

DETECTION IN THE CONTACTS AT LOW TEMPERATURES: EFFECT OF THE FREE ELECTRON CONCENTRATION ON THE DETECTING PARAMETERS

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Abstract

Diode detectors (DDs) are widely used in electronic information and communication systems. In this paper, the numerical modeling of the electrical potential distribution and current passing in the contacts of a normal metal or a superconductor with a bismuth–antimony (Bi–Sb) semiconductor alloy has been conducted. The possibilities of designing DDs based on these contacts to operate at a temperature (T) of liquid helium of 4.2 K and 1 K have been explored. The dependences of current responsivity (CR), voltage responsivity (VR) and noise equivalent power (NEP) on the free electron concentration have been analyzed. The physical causes of these dependences have been examined. The effect the signal frequency (f) on the detecting parameters has been shown. The obtained results have been compared with the literature data. Comparison with the currently available literature data has shown that proposed DDs can be 1–2 orders better. The physical reasons for these advantages have been discussed. It has been shown that the unique properties of Bi–Sb alloys, particularly the $\text{Bi}_{0.88}\text{Sb}_{0.12}$ alloy, make these alloys promising materials for cryoelectronics.

1. Introduction

Diode detectors (DDs) play an important role in radio technique and electronics. The use of high frequencies (above 1 GHz) has stimulated a thorough study of Schottky-barrier diodes. These diodes are based on quick-acting metal–semiconductor contacts [1].

A further improvement of the parameters of diodes was achieved due to a decrease in the operating temperature [2]. This direction is referred to as cryoelectronics [3]; it provides an increase in the nonlinearity of the current–voltage dependences and current responsivity (CR). The thermal noise power decreases too. For example, DDs based on Pb–pGaAs contacts have been developed [4, 5]. At a signal frequency of $f = 9$ GHz and $T = 4.2$ K, these diodes had $\text{CR} \approx 500$ A/W and a noise equivalent power (NEP) of 5×10^{-15} W/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$.

In addition, deep cooling allows using the materials with a narrow energy gap and a high electron mobility, such as Bi–Sb solid solutions [3, 6].

After the discovery of the high temperature superconductors (HTSCs), the possibilities of using HTSC in cryoelectronics were studied. At the liquid nitrogen temperature of $T = 77$ K and a signal frequency of $f = 37.5$ GHz, the respective structures exhibited a voltage responsivity (VR) of 3000 V/W [7]. Further studies [8] provided the design of structures with $\text{VR} = 5000$ V/W and $\text{NEP} = 2 \times 10^{-12}$ W/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at a signal frequency of $f = 31$ GHz and a temperature of $T = 77$ K.

According to our publication [9], the DDs based on HTSC–InSb contacts can have $CR \approx 40$ A/W, $VR \approx 10^6$ V/W, and $NEP \approx 8 \times 10^{-15}$ W/ \sqrt{Hz} at $T = 77.4$ K and $f = 10$ GHz. At the same temperature and $f = 30$ GHz, these DDs can have $CR \approx 15$ A/W, $VR \approx 3.5 \times 10^5$ V/W, and $NEP \approx 2 \times 10^{-14}$ W/ \sqrt{Hz} at a contact area of $100 \mu\text{m}^2$; however, a reduction in the contact area makes it possible to improve these parameters.

On the other hand, the semiconductor in HTSC–semiconductor contacts frequently undergoes oxidation because oxygen is an integral part of a HTSC. In addition, cooling to the liquid nitrogen temperature of 77.4 K can be insufficient to obtain good DD parameters. In this situation, taking into account the rapid development of cryogenics, a study of DDs based on conventional superconductor–semiconductor contacts seems to be an urgent problem. Typically, DDs operate at liquid helium temperatures ($T \leq 4.2$ K) [10, 11]. In this study, DDs based on the contacts of a superconductor (or a normal metal) with a Bi–Sb semiconductor solid solution are discussed.

2. Results and Discussion

Contacts of the $\text{Bi}_{0.88}\text{Sb}_{0.12}$ semiconductor solid solution with a normal metal or a superconductor were considered (for a contact area of $100 \mu\text{m}^2$). Aluminum at $T \geq 1.2$ K and silver or gold at lower temperatures can be used as the normal metal. Niobium or niobium nitride (NbN) can be chosen as superconductors at liquid helium temperatures. Properties of the materials were taken from [12–14]. Results of calculations for contacts with a normal metal are shown in Figs. 1–3. In these figures, a logarithmic scale for both axes is used. An exponential form is commonly used for numbers of axes.

Figure 1 shows the calculated dependence of CR on the free electron concentration in $\text{Bi}_{0.88}\text{Sb}_{0.12}$.

Fig. 1. Calculated dependence of CR on the free electron concentration in $\text{Bi}_{0.88}\text{Sb}_{0.12}$ at a signal frequency of $f = 1$ GHz and $T = 4.2$ K.

Initially, the CR increases with an increase in the free electron concentration because the ohmic volume resistance drops faster than the contact capacity resistance. This effect increases the signal voltage applied to the contact and the signal power absorbed in the contact and transformed in the rectified current.

However, an increase in the free electron concentration above 10^{21}m^{-3} it leads to an

increase in the barrier permeability, because the barrier width decreases. This fact reduces the nonlinearity of the current voltage, and the CR decreases.

Figure 2 shows the calculated dependence of VR on the free electron concentration in $\text{Bi}_{0.88}\text{Sb}_{0.12}$. In our case, inequality $r \ll R_c$ is fulfilled (r is the ohmic volume resistance; R_c is the contact differential resistance). In this situation [1], we can assume that $\text{VR} \approx \text{CR} \times R_c$.

Fig. 2. Calculated dependence of VR on the free electron concentration. Other data are similar to those in Fig. 1.

As the free electron concentration increases, the barrier permeability increases (see above) and the contact differential resistance decreases. The VR also decreases. If the free electron concentration is less than 10^{21} m^{-3} , the enlargement of the CR limits this effect.

However, if the free electron concentration is more than 10^{21} m^{-3} , the CR decreases and the VR rapidly decreases.

Figure 3 shows the calculated dependence of NEP on the free electron concentration in $\text{Bi}_{0.88}\text{Sb}_{0.12}$. This value increases with an increase in the free electron concentration, because the noise current sufficiently increases.

However, in a concentration range of 10^{20} to 10^{21} m^{-3} , this effect is diminished due to a rapid increase in the CR (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 3. Calculated dependence of NEP on the free electron concentration. Other data are similar to those in Fig. 1.

If the metal is replaced by a superconductor, the DD parameters are significantly improved [15]. The respective results are shown in Figs. 4 and 5.

The effect is particularly pronounced when the working temperature decrease from 4.2 to 1 K and the current passes due to the field emission regime [3]. In this regime, electrons near the Fermi level bring the main contribution to the contact current. However, at cryogenic temperatures, the properties of these electrons hardly depend on temperature; therefore, their current also hardly depends on temperature. In this case, in contacts with normal metals, the nonlinearity of the current–voltage characteristic (CVC) and the CR hardly depend on temperature [1, 3].

However, in contacts with superconductors, due to unique tunneling properties of superconductor [3], the CVC nonlinearity increases and the DD parameters are especially improved (compare curves 1 and 2 in Figs. 4, 5). This effect increases at a larger energy gap of the superconductor (see curves 2, 3 in Figs. 4, 5). This fact points out the necessity to select a superconductor with a wide energy gap (for example, NbN).

This effect is particularly pronounced in Fig. 6, which shows the initial portions of the CVCs for the NbN–Bi_{0.88}Sb_{0.12} contact. The CVCs for the normal metal–Bi_{0.88}Sb_{0.12} contact nearly coincide with curve 1 in Fig. 6, and they are not shown.

Fig. 4. Calculated dependence of CR on the signal frequency in contacts with Bi_{0.88}Sb_{0.12}. Curves 1, 2, and 3 correspond to the contacts with a normal metal, niobium, and niobium nitride, respectively. $T = 4.2$ K.

Fig. 5. Calculated dependence of CR on the signal frequency. The legend inscriptions are similar to those in Fig. 4. $T = 1$ K.

Fig. 6. Initial portions of the CVCs for the NbN–Bi_{0.88}Sb_{0.12} contact; $T = (1)$ 4.2 and (2) 1 K. I is the current density (in A/m²), V is the applied voltage (in mV).

Figures 4 and 5 show that the CR decreases and the NEP increases at frequencies above 3 GHz. At these frequencies, the negative role of the barrier capacity is revealed; it begins to shunt the nonlinear contact resistance. The current redistribution occurs; it leads to a decrease in the rectified current, and the DD parameters become worse.

Taking into account results of [4, 5, 7–9], we can conclude that contacts with Bi–Sb provide a significant improvement in DD parameters. They are much more effective than HTSC–superconductor contacts [7–9, 13]. In addition, they are better than contacts with GaAs [4, 5] operating at the liquid helium temperature.

The main advantages of Bi–Sb are as follows:

(i) Small barrier heights due to a narrow energy gap. This fact provides a considerable nonlinearity of the CVC and a high CR.

(ii) Extremely high electron mobility, which leads to a decrease in the ohmic resistance and improves the frequency properties.

(iii) At the same contact area and barrier permeability, the contact capacity in structures with Bi_{0.88}Sb_{0.12} is 4 times less than that for contacts with GaAs, which is one of the best materials of cryoelectronics. This fact is attributed to small barrier heights and small effective masses of electrons; these features also improve the frequency properties.

These unique properties of Bi–Sb alloys, particularly of the Bi_{0.88}Sb_{0.12} alloy, make these alloys promising materials for cryoelectronics.

3. Conclusions

The obtained results show that parameters of DDs based on contacts with Bi–Sb can be sufficiently improved due to selection of an optimum doping level and especially due to the use of contacts with superconductors. The physical reasons for these effects are discussed.

Analysis of our results [9–1, 15] shows that the proposed DDs (based on contacts with

Bi–Sb) may have a 2 times higher CR and a 50 times lower NEP than the the respective parameters of the currently available DDs (at the same temperature and signal frequency). In addition, they exhibit an extremely high VR. Their parameters can be a few orders of magnitude better than those of DDs operating at the liquid nitrogen temperature. This fact suggests that the preparation of contacts with Bi–Sb is promising.

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